

Brand Position Communication Channel for Rajabhat University

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Abstract—The objective of this research was to study Brand Position Communication Channel in Brand Building in Rajabhat University Affecting Decision Making of Higher Education from of qualitative research and in-depth interview with executive members Rajabhat University and also quantitative by questionnaires which are personal data of students, study of the acceptance and the finding of the information of Rajabhat University, study of pattern or Brand Position Communication Channel affecting the decision making of studying in Rajabhat University and the result of the communication in Brand Position Communication Channel. It is found that online channel and word of mouth are highly important and necessary for education business since media channel is a tool and the management of marketing communication to create brand awareness, brand credibility and to achieve the high acclaim in terms of bringing out qualified graduates. Also, off-line channel can enable the institution to survive from the high competition especially in education business regarding management of the Rajabhat University. Therefore, Rajabhat University has to communicate by the various communication channel strategies for brand building for attractive student to make decision making of higher education.

Keywords—Brand Position, Communication Channel, Rajabhat University.

I. INTRODUCTION

ADVERTISING is a series of appeals, symbols and statements deliberately designed to influence the receiver of the message toward the point of view desired by communication, and to act in some specific ways as a result of receiving the message, whether it will be to purchase vote, hold positive or negative views or merely maintain a memory. Also, advertising is not always in the best interest of the receiver of the message [3].

The field of advertising is in a state of transition, primarily because of the large changes taking place in the media environment. Traditional mass media advertising aimed at large, anonymous audiences may be a dying communication form.

Social marketing is about individual behavior. It is about “blaming the victim” of systems that push bad products and bad behaviors at them all the time. The solution is not to blame the victim, but advocate for the victim. It is not to change the individual but make it more difficult for the individual to be victimized. [2]

Mass media has the ability to influence people’s opinion and behavior. Nowadays, mass media is perceived as something that can stimulate preference, attitude and value

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judgment and behavior of the receiver. However, categories of mass media enable people to accept one more than the other. For instance, advertisements on television have more variety and specific characteristics that easily persuade the viewers to understand the message. Advertisements are commercial and market-oriented, aimed at hard selling product. Overtime, however, advertisements seem to change its thrust. It slowly shifts to social marketing which aims to develop awareness among people and make them realize that they can help solve problems in their society.

At present, communication technologies tend to revolutionize mass media, enabling them to play an important part in society or in people's lives. Mass media could lead and play an effective role in making people realize the appropriate response to societal problems, such as violence, drug abuse, safe sex etc.[1]

Most of the dwellers of the Bangkok Metropolis are frequently exposed to corporate advertising on environmental topics. They give most attention to topics like air pollution, water pollution and deforestation. They tend to realize the significance of problems and have the inclination to participate in any activities which many lead to the solution, the prevention and the conservation of the environment

Social marketing aims to promote responsibility in society by producing advertisements to develop people’s awareness, to encourage a change in ideology or lifestyle, and to generate a behavior that is considered more acceptable in society, such as non-smoking, drug abuse prevention, and promoting good relations in family [4]. Social marketing is based on the assumptions that there are behaviors worth changing and that it is society’s responsibility to help people make the right choices [2].

The consensus on both of these propositions is eroding. Social marketing is, after all, a robust technology of behavior change. Hardly perfect, but it is impressive in its strategic coherence, nonetheless.

However, the political consensus that supported and funded much work is falling apart. Even for those who do not rely entirely on public funds, access to public funds made some of the best and most important work possible [2].

II. METHODOLOGY

The Objectives of This Research

1. To study the process Procedures and communication strategies to build brand name Rajabhat University.
2. To study the factors those affect the branding of private higher education institutions.

Research Hypotheses

Based on literature survey the following hypotheses have been derived:

1. Different personal characteristics affect the Brand Position Communication Channel.
2. Communication Channel relate to the Brand Position For Rajabhat University

Fig. 1 Conceptual Framework

In this study will provide a conceptual framework for communication channel mixed will use Phillip Kotler (2000) and refer to brand position communication channel by the product, brand, distributor, time buying period-level of price designed within a communication channel follow by this framework [3].

III. FINDING

This part discussed the general demographic data. It focused on sex, age, allowance, Residential status of students. It will illustrate that the majority (62.25%) of the students were females, while males were only 37.75 percent. Half of them (51.25%) were 18 years old, followed by 19 years (45.75%), and the rest (3.00%) were 17 years old. The majority (41.50%) of students had an allowance of over 6,000 baht/month. Some (40.00%) receive between 5,001-6,000 baht per month, while others (8.00%) get a monthly allowance of 4,001-5,000 baht.

The majority of students lived alone (42.00%), usually in the school dormitory, while others rent a place with their friends (34.25%).it can be gleaned that majority (88.25%) of the students received the information of advertises on television concerning social marketing activities from the television. Fifty-six percent get exposed to social marketing issues from the newspaper, while less than half of the students (48.50%) received information from the radio.

Information was also solicited regarding the students' opinion on the social relevance of advertisements being aired on television regularly and will shows that the majority

(84.25%) believed that the "TAT" advertisement presents an issue that is socially relevant. Many (58.50%) of them, likewise saw that the "DTAC" advertisement conveys a message that is important to society. Other (47.50%) students

had also attitudes that the advertisement on "Boon Rawd Brewery" portrays information that has social relevance. [4] It is clearly shown that majority (97.00%) of the students received the information of advertises concerning social marketing activities from television, particularly from companies like DTAC, TAT, Boon Rawd Brewery, etc. Sixty-four percent said that they get informed by socially relevant advertisements from sources other than the ones listed above.

However, they did not specify these media sources. While others (62.25%) claimed that their neighbors are good sources of information on relevant social marketing activities. [5] When asked how often they see the advertisement on television concerning social marketing activities, 191(47.75%) mentioned they view the advertisements 3-4 times / week.

Sixty-nine students were able to see the advertisements every day, while only 13.75 percent mentioned that they got exposed to the advertisement 1-2 times/week [4].

After that it will illustrate that majority (71.00%) of the students watched advertises on television concerning social marketing activities in the late afternoon, particularly between 16.00-17.00 hours. Almost 70.00 percent view socially-relevant advertises on television 18.00-19.00 hours, while the others (68.75%) were able to see these advertisements in the midevening, particularly between 20.00-21.00 hours.

TABLE I
 FREQUENCY PER DAY OF EXPOSURE ADVERTISES ON TELEVISION
 CONCERNING SOCIAL MARKETING ACTIVITIES

Items	Do not Watch (percent)	Watch (percent)
The frequency of time spent per day		
1 time/day	9.25	90.75
1-2 time/day	42.00	58.00
3-4 time/day	22.50	77.50
5-6 time/day	26.00	74.00
Over 6 time/day	33.50	66.50

(n=400)

Students were also asked how often they view the television advertises on social marketing activities on a daily basis. Results indicated that majority (90.75%) were able to watch these advertisements once a day. Many (77.50%) also admitted that they see the advertisements 3-4 times/day, while 74.00 percent cited that they frequently see these advertises on television, usually 5-6 times/day which accounted for 296 (74.00%).

TABLE II
DEGREE OF STUDENT^a ATTITUDE TOWARDS ADVERTISES ON TELEVISION CONCERNING SOCIAL MARKETING ACTIVITIES
(n=400)

Statements	Level Of Agreement					Mean	S.D.	Attitude Level
	1	2	3	4	5			
Clarify content more understanding on Thai tradition and culture	168 (42)	2 (0.50)	172 (43)	43 (10.75)	15 (3.75)	2.34	1.23	less
more understanding on the worth of low class people	0 (0)	92 (23)	112 (28)	196 (49)	0 (0)	3.26	0.81	medium

From Table II, it could be seen that the degree of students' attitude towards advertises on television concerning social marketing activities was classified in the medium level, as depicted by the mean 3.13. In addition, it could be concluded that the students' attitude was favorable in terms of how the advertises were presented, as indicated by the mean of 3.21. The students also felt that they advertise had a clear content, as this item obtained a mean of 3.14. Similarly, the students' attitude towards the advertisement after being exposed to them, seemed Favorable, too, as depicted by the mean 3.37.

IV. DISCUSSION/SUGGESTIONS

The study made use of the survey research design, employing a questionnaire as the instrument for collecting data from the sample. The sample consisted of Rajabhat University students pursuing bachelor degrees at the Suan Sunandha campus. The sample size of the study was calculated at 400 students based from the population of 5,231.

After data have been collected, the researcher analyzed the data using descriptive and inferential statistical techniques, particularly frequency counts, percentile, mean, standard deviation, t-test, One way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and, Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient testing. [5]

Majority of the respondents was female, mostly 18 years old, followed by respondents who were 19 years old. Many of them belonged to the Agriculture and Engineering Faculty, pursuing bachelor degrees in Agricultural Science, Architecture, Social Science, and Agriculture Industrial Science. Majority of the respondents received an allowance of over 6,000 baht/month, while some of get between 5,001-6,000 baht per month. Most of them lived alone in the school dormitories, and others were staying with their friends

Majority of the respondents received information about advertises on television concerning social marketing activities from the television, followed by newspaper and then radio. Most of them knew about television advertises on television concerning social marketing activities. The majority deemed that "TAT unseen in Thailand" conveys a message that is socially relevant. They received information about advertisements concerning social marketing activities (e.g. DTAC, TAT, Boon Rawd Brewery) from television, others sources, and from their friends. Majority of the respondents saw advertises on television concerning social marketing activities 3-4 times/week, between 16.00-17.00 hours. Most of them, however, were only able to watch once a day. [5]

The degree of students' attitude towards advertises on television concerning social marketing activities is said to be in the medium level. Nevertheless, respondents exhibited favorable attitude in terms of the advertisement presentation, clarity of content, and the students' attitude after being exposed to the advertisement on television concerning social marketing activities [3].

There is no significant difference between sex, age, allowance (baht/month), residential status and the degree of attitude towards television advertisements concerning social marketing activities.

There is a significant difference between faculty where students belonged and exposure to media source and the degree of attitude towards television advertisements concerning social marketing activities. [4]

V. RECOMMENDATION FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

Findings of this study have shown that the students' degree program and exposure to particular media sources affect his or her attitude toward television advertises on television concerning social marketing activities.

Therefore, this point can be useful for students, particularly those who came from the province and whose family is working on agriculture. Agriculture students seemed to be more concerned with the concept or idea of social marketing activities, as shown in their attitude towards the DTAC series "same heart". This advertisement shows Thai values and traditions that reflect honor and gratitude. It is concerned with social marketing activities [2] that implied humble worship and apologies for a rice goddess from a folk tale.

More importantly, it is observed that students nowadays are exposed to and easily adapt to foreign ways. This results to the dwindling of old Thai tradition, such as being generous or promoting domestic, but economically oriented activities. Thus, advertising companies should create an interesting campaign to persuade young people to still practice old traditions and values. In general, suggestions should be done on how they can change their attitude or behavior to conduct socially relevant activities [4].

In conclusion, students accept these kinds of advertisements. They have a positive attitude towards television advertisements concerning social marketing activities. They claimed that these types of advertises would enable them to change their attitude and behavior, as a result of their being affected by its content or method of presentation.

However, there is a question whether some social marketing activities is aimed to persuade other groups of audience. Thus, it could be possible to explore more on attitudes of parents' group, friends' group, or working people's group [5].

The study suggested that most students who perceived the television advertisements concerning social marketing activities cited that there should be a corresponding change in attitude or behavior on the part of the viewer or receiver of information. Thus, it is also recommended that an in-depth study can be done on the behavioral effects of advertises on television concerning social marketing activities, and its effects on the efficiency of conducting social marketing activities [4].

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REFERENCES

- [1] Kotler, P. (2003). Marketing management: Setting the product and branding strategy 14th ed. New Jersey: Prentice – Hall.
- [2] Kotler,P.& Armstrong (2006). Principles of marketing. 11th ed.. New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
- [3] ChenjitJangjankij (2007) "IMC & Marketing Communication.
- [4] Duenden Nuraram (2009)"Marketing strategy and marketing communications of the shopping center. Siam Center Siam Discovery Center and Siam Paragon.
- [5] KamolChaiwat(2009)" Recognition Integrated Marketing Communications (IMC) of the consumer to buy a product (Organic Product)" Sripatum University.